

VICTIM VS. ACCUSED: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF RIGHT TO FAIR TRIAL

Abdullah^{1*}, Aniq Munir², Suheer Ahmad³

¹LLM (Constitutional Law), 2022-24, Postgraduate School of Legal Studies, University of the Punjab, LLB (Hons.) 2016-21, University Law College, University of the Punjab, MA- International Relations, 2019-21, Department of Political Science, University of the Punjab, Quaid-i-Azam Campus, Lahore, Pakistan.

²M.Phil. International Relations, 2023-25, Department of Political Science, MA- International Relations, 2019-21, Department of Political Science, LLB (Hons.) 2018-23, University Law College, University of the Punjab, Quaid-i-Azam Campus, Lahore, Pakistan.

³LLM (Constitutional Law), 2022-24, Postgraduate School of Legal Studies, University of The Punjab, LLB (Hons.) Sharia and Law, 2017-22, International Islamic University Islamabad, Pakistan

*¹abdullahbhatti7068836@gmail.com, ²aniqamunir137@gmail.com, ³advsuheerahmad@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14904381>

Keywords

Fair Trial, Victim's Right, Criminal Justice System, Criminal Jurisprudence.

Article History

Received on 13 January 2025

Accepted on 13 February 2025

Published on 21 February 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

The right to fair trial is essential and fundamental right which require that a trial should be conducted in fair manner, however, the development and evolution of the doctrine of right to fair trial has, significantly, created an imbalance between the rights of accused and victim. This lopsidedness is inherently linked with the evolution of the doctrine of fair trial in adversarial system as a conflict between the state power and the accused where the crime is seen as against the state: Previously the crime against king. This imbalance not only remained visible but also increases throughout the historical evolution of the idea that accused must be protected as against the mighty power of state. This disturbance in equilibrium, in the early 1970's, was started to be acknowledged by policy makers, jurists, judges and various law reforms committees which resulted in various legislations. However, this lopsidedness still exists and especially within the context of Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

The trial's main purpose is to determine whether the accusations are true and to punish the actual offender. One of the most important and prestigious rights is the right to a fair trial. It includes a variety of rights required to conduct a trial reasonably. It is undeniable that the development of the right to a fair trial has diminished the significance of victims' rights. It has mostly been observed from the accused side, particularly in the criminal domain (Singh & Zahan, 2022). Its evolution from the seventeenth century restricts significant rights of victims in adversarial trials, rather than seeing this right as

offering equal benefits to both the accused and the victim (Kirchengast, 2006b).

Fair trial is guaranteed by Article 10A. However, this exclusive clause does not address the victim or the accused; rather, it simply protects the accused's rights. Despite substantial legislative flaws, the paper makes it abundantly evident that victim rights are seriously lacking in our existing judicial system and that call into question whether a trial can be deemed fair. A constitutional right emphasises both its obligation and its right (Karim, 2003). Such a duty can only be met if the state, which is required to see the trial through to its logical end, guarantees victims' equal

rights, effective investigation, and appropriate prosecution. It is not appropriate to leave a trial to the state alone because it is an important matter, particularly when governmental institutions are rotten and utterly incapable of delivering justice (Ishaq, n.d.).

Therefore, the victim should have the freedom to provide their narrative of the facts in addition to the state's account, rather than being forced to rely only on the state apparatus. In addition to being able to freely express their viewpoint as a witness, this guarantees that the victim is fully informed about all court proceedings and has firsthand experience of the scenario. Indeed, victims are already represented by public prosecution and independent counsel, but the situation is more complicated than it seems. Since the victim is only able to testify in court and cannot express the extent of his suffering, his testimony is not taken into account for determining the appropriate minimum sentence.

A fair trial includes more than simply the trial itself; it is not finished until the whole procedure is equitable and gives the victim and the accused equal chances. The right to a fair trial extends beyond the trial itself; it is not complete unless the entire process is equitable and gives the victim and the accused equal opportunities. The rights of victims are being gravely threatened when the accused are granted the constitutional right to a fair trial while victims are not included in several significant processes, such as the investigation and the post-conviction phase. The victims' rights have not been adequately protected by the State alone, and relying just on the system to prosecute them can erode public trust in it.

Literature Review:

According to the Indian Supreme Court's ruling in *Zahira Habibullah Sheikh*, a fair trial is a fundamental human rights tenet that should be interpreted as a "triangulation of interest." Triangulation, as defined by the SC, refers to society as represented by the accused, victim, and state. The ruling further clarifies the idea of the right to a fair trial, concluding that it encompasses both pre-trial and post-trial proceedings and is not restricted to hearings before an unbiased judge (*Zahira Habibullah Sheikh vs State of Gujrat*, 2006).

Tyrone Kirchengest's seminal work on the rights of victims in court served as the foundation for this research. His in-depth research on the history of criminal trials, particularly with relation to victim representation and rights, was crucial to comprehending how the trial's dynamics changed over time (Kirchengast, 2006a).

An essential book that sheds further light on the victim's historical role and how its influence on the trial was later downplayed is *Victims and the Criminal Trial* (Kirchengast, 2006a).

Following independence, the criminal justice systems of India and Pakistan are nearly identical, having both inherited colonial legal systems. The criminal justice system in India has undergone numerous revisions, and numerous committees have attempted to recommend significant enhancements to the legal system. In this context, the Malimath Committee, also known as the Reforms Committee on Criminal Justice System 2003, is significant. Under the direction of a former Chief Justice of the Karnataka High Court, the group conducted a thorough analysis of the Indian justice system and the reasons behind its shortcomings. The Committee discussed about reforming the colonial judicial system and shared its opinions on the victim's place in the system.

It's crucial to read about victims' rights in criminal trials. The article emphasises how the state and the accused play different roles during the trial. Along with discussing the limitations of the rights that could be granted to victims in an adversarial system, the paper also discusses the practical difficulties of doing so. The article is crucial for identifying issues with our judicial system. The paper doesn't highlight any problematic statutes or offer any workable legal changes to improve the system's balance (Doak, 2005).

One significant document that outlines victims' rights is the United States Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime. This stipulates that victims have the right to access justice, reparation, and fair and prompt redress (United Nations, 1985)

In his piece, Muhammad Ather Waheed outlines significant issues that Pakistani victims of crime face, such as the unprofessional conduct of police, the prosecution's lacklustre role in criminal cases, and

the prejudice of the courts, which has a significant impact on the outcome of the trial. All of these issues can be resolved by not just reforming the system but also by giving victims more authority and guaranteeing their representation throughout the entire pre-trial and post-trial process. The essay does not address any statutory shortcomings or offer any helpful adjustments to address the system, despite its importance in elucidating and emphasizing victims' suffrage in the existing legal environment (Waheed, 2009).

This significant article chronicles the development of the victim's rights and fair trial rights movements, as well as their outcomes in the United States and around the world. This article also looks at several movements that pushed for global legislation on these issues and truly broadened the scope of victims' rights, which is crucial to understanding how this idea has developed globally (Goddu, 1993).

Research Question:

Does the right to a fair trial disproportionately favor the accused over the victim?

Limitations:

Undoubtedly, the concept of a fair trial has a long history and continuously evolved. Without addressing how it is applied in civil law matters, this study solely examines the evolution of the right to a fair trial under criminal law. The study's scope would be limited to diagnosing the issues and drawing attention to the presence of conflict between the rights of victims and the accused at. The research offers no recommendations, potential fixes, or a path forward.

Discussion:

1- Fair Trial: Conceptual Understanding, Definition and Scope:

Concept:

Societies have established a set of rights to give the accused a fair trial. The right to a fair trial covers these rights. Among the essential tenets of natural justice is the right to a fair trial. Although the term "fair" was initially used in trials in the 17th century, it wasn't until the 19th century that courts began using it frequently. In its early years, the trial was seen as

"free from blemish (Langford, 2009)." To shield people against the capricious use of state authority, the right to a fair trial is a fundamental component of international human rights law (Jelena & Vanessa, 2000).

Definition:

Ensuring the accused receives equal protection and representation is the aim of this right. It means that the accused must be granted certain rights so that he may defend himself to prove his guilt or when the responsibility owed to another party is being determined. According to the Black Law Dictionary, this word refers to a trial conducted by a neutral, disinterested tribunal using standard processes, particularly a criminal trial where the defendant's legal and constitutional rights are upheld. It is also known as a fair and unbiased trial. The idea that the judicial system should not crush the innocent is the foundation of a fair trial (Teka, 2023).

Scope:

Contrary to what its name suggests, the right to a fair trial extends beyond the trial. A criminal trial begins when the charges are framed and concludes with a verdict. A trial is only one aspect of the right to a fair trial; pre-trial and post-trial actions are also included. The pre-trial procedures consist of inquiry, investigation, and case registration. Pretrial procedures must also be conducted under the law to be fair. Criminal activity must not corrupt the foundation upon which the trial will be held; otherwise, the entire process may be called into question. Since the investigation is regarded as the cornerstone of the case, it must always be conducted fairly. However, according to the Sindh High Court, the investigation is the cornerstone of the case, and to ensure justice, the informant and the investigating officer must be distinct (Mohsin V. The State, 2023). In the case of Bennett v. Horseferry Road Magistrates, the House of Lords ordered the defendant, a New Zealand citizen who was accused of committing crimes in England and who the English police had tracked down in South Africa before forcing him back to England, to remain in the proceedings and release the offender who had not been arrested under the law (R v Horseferry Road Magistrates Court ex parte Bennett, 1994). Fair trial

rights have not been granted to Justice Shaukat Aziz Siddique since he has not been given access to an inquiry procedure (2024 SCP 112).

The investigation, which comes before the trial, must be fair before the trial can be fair. Due to poor investigations, the majority of trials end without a conviction. Likewise, the right to appeal is included in the fair trial right, which the court has deemed to be a substantive right (*Pakistan Defence Officer's Housing Authority v Jawaid Ahmed*, 2013).

According to the Supreme Court in *Vinubhai Haribhai Malaviya* (2019), "a trial encompasses investigation, inquiry, trial, appeal, and re-trial, i.e., the entire scrutiny including crime detection and adjudication...." (*Vinubhai Haribhai Malaviya v. The State of Gujarat*, 2019).

2- Fair Trial in Pakistan:

The idea behind a fair trial is to give the accused the ability to defend themselves more effectively and present a strong case against the powerful state. Historians identify its origins in the Magna Carta, even though it existed in many forms among the customs and laws of ancient communities. Later, as time passed, the right changed. The United States of America was the first country to include the right to a fair trial in its constitution when the Sixth and Fourteenth Amendments were added. Through the UDHR, which Pakistan also ratified, it was acknowledged as a universal right in 1948. The rights to due process and a fair trial are guaranteed to the accused by Article 10A of the Pakistani constitution. Before Article 10A was added, the SC declared that the right to a fair trial is only a philosophical idea and that no statute may be declared unconstitutional based on that idea alone (*F.B. Ali v State*, 1975).

Since Article 10A was added, the theory's importance has grown, and the State is now required to act within the bounds of the right to a fair trial (*JAWWAD S. KHAWAJA versus FEDERATION OF PAKISTAN*, 2024).

The rights outlined in Articles 12(1), 13(a), and 13(b) are all included in the more comprehensive fair trial right. Additionally, it covers the right to life and liberty under Article 9 as well as equal protection under Article 25.

3- Lopsidedness in Right to Fair Trial:

It frequently appears that the right to a fair trial is biased in favour of the defence in criminal trials. Victims in our legal system are left to rely on incompetent and uninterested public prosecutors as well as insufficient and ineffectual police investigations (Ishaq, n.d.).

A reflection of this reality is the low conviction rate. Victims who engage private solicitors are not allowed to directly assist the police in collecting evidence or defending a case without the public prosecutor's approval and supervision. The victim, in other words, cannot change the outcome of a case that ends in acquittal because of inadequate police investigation and prosecution. Throughout the proceedings, the victim is only allowed to testify as a prosecution witness and is not permitted to express his complaints. In a system where the victim is bearing the consequences of poor investigation and prosecution, where the accused's rights are guaranteed by the constitution, and where natural justice principles are consistently used in his favour, could a trial like that ever be deemed fair?

4- Why there is an Imbalance:

It is debatable why criminal jurisprudence evolved to exclude victims from the trial process. The legal system's development holds the key to the solution. Because the early criminal justice system did not treat the offence as a crime against the state, the state did not punish the victim; rather, the offence was a dispute between people. In the Anglo-Saxon era, the victim was merely used as a witness to the crime and the offence was viewed as a crime against the king (Wemmers, 2012). The concept of including a victim in a criminal trial is not new; rather, the role of a criminal has changed over time. In the eleventh century, the victim was essential to the prosecution's efforts to identify the suspect and bring the criminals to justice (Kirchengast, 2006c).

Evidence Connected with Historical Evolution:

The British monarchy has given way to the modern democracy and the present criminal justice system. The person, especially the one who has been accused, was always weaker in front of the strong king in a monarchy where the king has absolute power. In response, society gave the accused the bare minimum of guarantees. Alongside this, societal integration

started to change. In the thirteenth century, victims' involvement in criminal trials began to wane. The parliament started to solidify its authority in the fourteenth century. Individuals gained significant rights with the change of power. In criminal procedures, they assert significant protection against the king's hegemony (Caenegem, 2014).

However, the victim's authority to bring charges against the accused declined as a result of the parliament's legislation and monarch's ascent. An important turning point was reached in 1437 when the first royal prosecutor was appointed. His job was to oversee state prosecutions and make sure justice was carried out efficiently (Prosecutor General's Office, n.d.).

On behalf of the state, the Public Prosecutor took on the victim's role and handled the case. Being in charge of the residents' lives and property, the state made sure that the accused would not be denied a fair trial and that the trial's goal would continue to be punishing the guilty rather than seeking revenge or retribution. In the end, these elements reduced the victim's involvement in the trial and gave the State prosecution authority. The weak victim was able to obtain justice because to this systemic reform, but it also left him completely reliant on the government. In addition to upsetting the victim, any state failure or neglect throws off the equilibrium of what is known as a fair trial.

Monarchies have given way to constitutional monarchies and then to democratic systems around the world. Individuals gained significant rights with the change of power. They would assert significant protection in criminal procedures from the king's dominion. The emergence of state power has been interpreted by various victimologists and criminologists as limiting victims' access to courts and, eventually, criminal prosecutions (Caenegem, 2014). Therefore, the accused's poor position against the state serves as justification for granting him rights (Zahan & Singh, 2022). The accused is granted many rights that arise during a criminal trial to shield him from the powerful state and to prevent erroneous verdicts (*R v Carroll*, 2002). The right to a fair trial is regarded as including the following legally enforceable rights: the right to be silent, the right to a fair investigation, the right to double jeopardy, the right to be aware of the charges, and the right to be

aware of the evidence presented against oneself (Hashimy, 2023). On the other hand, the Victims have always been viewed by the legal system as part of the prosecution. The victim cannot assist the court by interrogating witnesses or offering evidence. In some way, history is the cause of this.

Why in Pakistan:

In any case, prior to the East India Company, India's statutory and informal legal systems had adequately taken into account the victims of the crime. The victim has to present their own proof in the Panchayat System. He or his legal heirs were given the respect they deserved, but he was just seen as a witness to the catastrophe. His suffering was appropriately acknowledged, and society as a whole used to help him. Without any obstacles, they were permitted to make their case. Both sides would be heard by Qazis or kings in an official setting. They were given a fair chance to voice their opinions. With the arrival of Britishers the same jurisprudence and the adversarial system started to develop in the British India which caused this disturbed equilibrium between the rights of accused and victim in fair trial. Primarily, the battle is between the state in form of prosecution and the accused being a vulnerable in front of mighty power of state.

In the light of above discussion describing the history and evolution of adversarial criminal justice system and continuation of the same jurisprudence after independence is the cause of this imbalance which is justified by the understanding that accused frequently find themselves in vulnerable situations, which naturally necessitates defensive measures. These accused who are considered to be opponent of mighty power of state, furthermore, unable to win society's sympathies has become the focus of right to fair trail suppressing the rights of victims.

Evidence in form of Acknowledgment:

The presence of lopsidedness in the concept and scope of right to fair trail can also be perceived as this was highlighted in various form and the acknowledgment of this imbalance in different forms. Different countries acknowledging this imbalance took different steps in form of legislation. Moreover, the various policy recommendations by committees and court judgments highlighting this issue are evidence of presence of imbalance which supports the question of research in affirmative way.

The concept of a fair trial has undergone a paradigm shift since the 1960s. Following the shift, other nations started passing legislation to guarantee victims a fair trial. Examples of these include the Victims of Crimes Assistance Act of Victoria, the Victim and Witness Protection Act of 1982, the Crime Victim Rights Act of 2004 in the United States, and the Criminal Injuries Act of 1995 in the United Kingdom.

Even President Ronald Reagan emphasised how the state fails to give victims justice and how the ongoing concern with the accused's rights has had a significant negative influence on victims' rights (Reagan Library, 2017). According to the unanimous conclusion of a task team that Reagan established, the system "regularly re-victimized the victims"(Hook & Seymour, 2004). Following this, America's criminal jurisprudence adopted necessary rights through various statutes. Moreover, in 1985, a resolution on victims' rights was voted by the General Assembly. These developments and acknowledgments compliment the argument that the development and evolution of English jurisprudence caused this imbalance which was recognized by many countries and they started to legislate to balance this imbalance. Here the research paper is only to establish the presence of such lopsidedness only, without touching any recommendations in light of these developments in the world.

Lord Steyn emphasised that in criminal proceedings, the court must take the triangulation of interests into account (*Attorney-General's Reference (no3 of 1999)*, 2001). Triangulation of interest refers to the interests of society, the victim, and the accused. The victim plays a crucial role in a trial that is not just viewed as a conflict between two parties.

Our system is now hostile. Two parties are viewed as engaged in combat during an adversarial trial. Unfortunately, the aspect of this relationship that is not shown is the victim. When the accused's rights upset the victim's prejudice balance, the necessity for victims in a criminal trial was born. The victim has certain rights, just like the accused. The victim became a significant part of the trial as several criminologists examined the relationship between the accused and victim, the psychological effects of the crime on the witness, and the reasons behind that suffering after World War II (Karmen, 2024).

The Malimath Committee in India suggested many plans to engage victims as an essential part of the criminal justice process. The Code of Criminal Procedure Act of 2008 incorporated the majority of these suggestions (Malimath, 2003). To ensure that justice is done, the idea of a fair trial requires that the trial procedure be equitable; nevertheless, it cannot be fair if it favours one party in favour of another. The trial seeks to keep society safe and secure while also giving the victim justice. Except as a witness, the victim whose rights are infringed by the accused is not entitled to take part (Malimath, 2003). The Indian court attempted to give crime victims effective rights in conjunction with these modifications. The SCI did not weigh the victim's hearing against the prosecution in its ruling in *Jagjeet Singh v. Ashish Mishra*. The victim and the accused both have the right to a fair hearing, the court said.

According to the SCP, the right to a fair trial ensures that the victim and the guilty are treated equally in the legal system (*Amjad Mustafa Malik v. Director General NAB*, 2021). In a different case, the SC decided that a victim's right to a fair trial is compromised by drawing incorrect conclusions from any evidence, as per the opinion of Justice Ayesha Malik (*Muhammad Imran Vs. The State and another*, 2023).

Although society, represented by the state, is obligated to assist the victim or his legal representatives in an inquiry into the crime, this does not absolve the victim or turn him into a state prosecutor's witness. The Islamic structure gives the victim an equal chance at a fair trial and allows them to engage in the proceedings (*Federation of Pakistan through Secretary Vs. Gul Hassan*, 1989)

These evidence, mentioned above, due to historical development and evolution of common law and afterwards, also in the form of acknowledgments are enough to conclude that the presence of lopsidedness in the existing criminal justice system based on the jurisprudence developed and evolve in the context of adversarial system.

Conclusion:

Although the accused's rights have been upheld by the normative definition of a fair trial, the victim's participation in the trial process has frequently

suffered as a result. The victim has suffered since their position has been weakened as the accused's rights have increased. Moreover, according to the adversarial paradigm, the criminal trial is viewed as a fight between the prosecution and the defence. As victims' rights have grown, the fair trial idea must be modified to incorporate victims' rights. The victim must experience the fairness of the trial. Therefore, it is very necessary to provide victims with the protection of a fair trial. All of these rights were created and developed in the accused's favour, leaving the victim to wait for the state to resolve the matter in a way that makes sense.

As we've highlighted while discussing the scope of right to fair trial, a fair trial encompasses more than just the rights granted during the trial. Instead, it involves the pre-trial and post-trial processes. Therefore, the victim is entitled to rights from the start of the proceedings. He must receive the same level of attention and be informed at every inquiry stage. In Pakistan, the victim is reduced to the role of a witness for the prosecution

The rights of victims are not mentioned in any of the clauses pertaining to the right to a fair trial in international accords. This does not, however, mean that the victim's right to a fair trial can be restricted because there is no embargo on it in any of the international accords. Instead, they discuss giving the victim their rights. (Mezykowska, 2013). Moreover, there is a possibility that the victim's involvement in the trial could lead to additional issues, such as upsetting the trial's overall equilibrium. The legal system's goal makes the idea of victim participation rife with obstacles and challenges. One could argue that allowing the victim to interfere with the trial process would prevent an objective outcome. Likewise, if someone were a victim, the entire idea of innocence until proven guilty would be suppressed. Although these concerns are legitimate, they shouldn't stand in the way of enhancing victim participation and providing them with the advantages of a fair trial. As their participation in court proceedings helps the accused and the court remember and comprehend the consequences of doing the crime in real life, which supports the need for justice and accountability for the impacted parties as well as the legal system. Because the victim has a firsthand understanding of the case, victim

involvement has the impact of strengthening it. It is crucial in making sure that data is taken into account to provide impartiality throughout a trial. For the same reason, victims' participation in the trial system will increase public trust in the legal system. It maintains accountability and engages individuals, claiming that the system takes into account the accounts of those who have been harmed by crimes.

The state is required by Article 37 of the Pakistani Constitution to provide prompt, affordable justice. The article makes it available to all parties and does not limit it to just the accused. In a similar vein, the founders of the Constitution purposefully used the word justice. The definition of justice is "fairness in the way people are dealt with," which means that the state and all of its branches, including the judiciary, have a responsibility to safeguard victims' rights as well as the rights of the accused in criminal prosecution.

Numerous efforts have been made to enhance Pakistan's current body of jurisprudence. However, victim participation as a matter of right is still under question and a lot of work is needed as it is essential in criminal trials because it can help recreate the timeline of events, the motivations behind the crime, and the severity of the punishment. Because of their involvement, victims would feel they are acknowledged by the legal system. They can express the hostility they have experienced, which helps them to heal psychologically and speeds up the process. Therefore, including victims in the trial enhances the accused's culpability premise, among other factors.

REFERENCES:

Amjad Mustafa Malik v. Director General NAB, PLD 266 (Islamabad High Court 2021). [https://mis.ihc.gov.pk/frmRdJgmnt?cseNo=W.P.%20769/2019%20\(DB\)%20%7C%202021%20PLD%20266%20Islamabad&cseTl e=W.P.%20769/2019%20N.A.B.%20Bail%20\(Amjad%20Mustafa%20Malik%20V/s%20ODG,%20NAB%20etc\)&hx0025;20\(DB\)&j gs=Honourable%20Chief%20Justice%20Mr.%20Justice%20Athar%20Minallah,%20Honourable%20Mr.%20Justice%20Miangu%20Hassan%20Aurangzeb&jgmnt=/attachments/judgements/W.P-769-](https://mis.ihc.gov.pk/frmRdJgmnt?cseNo=W.P.%20769/2019%20(DB)%20%7C%202021%20PLD%20266%20Islamabad&cseTl e=W.P.%20769/2019%20N.A.B.%20Bail%20(Amjad%20Mustafa%20Malik%20V/s%20ODG,%20NAB%20etc)&hx0025;20(DB)&j gs=Honourable%20Chief%20Justice%20Mr.%20Justice%20Athar%20Minallah,%20Honourable%20Mr.%20Justice%20Miangu%20Hassan%20Aurangzeb&jgmnt=/attachments/judgements/W.P-769-)

- 2019_____6371
91724241191384.pdf
- Attorney-General's Reference (No3 of 1999), 2 AC 91 (2001). <https://vlex.co.uk/vid/attorney-general-s-reference-793041433>
- Caenegem, R. C. van. (2014). A note on chapter 39 of Magna Carta. *Fundamina*, 20(2), 961–964.
- CODE OF CONDUCT FOR PROSECUTORS, § 5.11 (2016). <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://pg.punjab.gov.pk/system/files/CODE%20OF%20CONDUCT%20FOR%20PROSECUTORS%20%28FINAL%29.pdf>
- CODE OF CRIMINAL PROCEDURE, § 493 (1898). [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.fmu.gov.pk/docs/laws/C](chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.fmu.gov.pk/docs/laws/Code_of_criminal_procedure_1898.pdf)
- Doak, J. (2005). Victims' Rights in Criminal Trials: Prospects for Participation. *Journal of Law and Society*, 32(2), 294–316.
- F.B. Ali v State, PLD 506 (Supreme Court of Pakistan 1975).
- Federation of Pakistan through Secretary Vs. Gul Hassan, PLD 633 (Supreme Court of Pakistan 1989). [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.federalshariatcourt.gov.p](chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.federalshariatcourt.gov.pk/Judgments/R.Sr.P.No.17.I.L.W.of.1989.pdf)
- Goddu, C. (1993). Victims' 'Rights' or a Fair Trial Wronged? *Buffalo Law Review*, 41(1), 245.
- Hashimy, S. Q. (2023). The Paradigm of Fair Trial in Adversarial System: A Legal Discourse. *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, 6(2), 3308–3330.
- Hook, M., & Seymour, A. (2004). *A Retrospective of the 1982 President's Task Force on Victims of Crime*. VC Archive. https://www.ncjrs.gov/ovc_archives/ncvrw/2005/pg4d.html
- Ishaq, H. H. (n.d.). *The Right to Fair Trial: Better Late than Never* | SAHSOL. LUMS. Retrieved 11 February 2025, from <https://sahsol.lums.edu.pk/node/12803>
- JAWWAD S. KHAWAJA versus FEDERATION OF PAKISTAN, PLD 337 (Supreme Court of Pakistan 2024).
- Jelena, P., & Vanessa, L. (2000). *What is a Fair Trial? A Basic Guide to Legal Standards and Practice*. Lawyers Committee for Human Rights. <https://hrea.org/resources/what-is-a-fair-trial-a-basic-guide-to-legal-standards-and-practice/>
- Karim, F. (2003). *Access to justice in Pakistan: A handbook of civil & criminal procedure with constitutional setting* (1st ed). Pakistan Law House. <https://searchworks.stanford.edu/view/8579971>
- Karmen, A. (2024). Victimology. In *Britannica*. Britannica. Victimology | Crime, Trauma & Prevention | Britannica', Encyclopædia Britannica (2024)
- Kirchengast, T. (2006a). The Victim as an Agent of Criminal Law and Justice. In T. Kirchengast (Ed.), *The Victim in Criminal Law and Justice* (pp. 218–230). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230625778_9
- Kirchengast, T. (2006b). *The Victim in Criminal Law and Justice*. Springer Nature Link. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1057/9780230625778>
- Kirchengast, T. (2006c). *The Victim in Criminal Law and Justice* (2006th edition). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Langford, I. (2009). Fair Trial: The History of an Idea. *Journal of Human Rights*, 8, 37–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14754830902765857>
- Malimath, J. V. S. (2003). *Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System* (No. 1; p. 306). Ministry of Home Affairs. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/2022-08/criminal_justice_system%5B1%5D.pdf
- Mezykowska, A. (2013). *Does the Victim of a Crime Have the Right to a Fair Trial? Remarks on the Protection of Crime Victims in the Light of the Guarantees in the European Convention on Human Rights* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No.

- 2218733). Social Science Research Network. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2218733>
- Mohsin V. The State, P Cr. L J 50 (2023).
- Muhammad Imran Vs. The State and Another, CrI.P. 752 (2023).
- Pakistan Defence Officer's Housing Authority v Jawaid Ahmed, SCMR 1707 (2013).
- Prosecutor General's Office. (n.d.). *History of Public Prosecution*. More about Public Prosecution. Retrieved 11 February 2025, from <https://verejnazaloba.cz/en/more-about-public-prosecution/history-of-public-prosecution/>
- R v Carroll, 213 CLR 635 (2002). <https://www.studocu.com/en-au/document/university-of-southern-queensland/advanced-criminal-law/r-v-carroll-2002-213-clr-635/101058060>
- R v Horseferry Road Magistrates Court Ex Parte Bennett, 1 A.C. 42 (1994). <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://iilj.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/Regina-v.-Horseferry-Road-Magistrates-Court-Ex-parte-Bennett.pdf>
- Reagan Library (Director). (2017, June 27). *President Reagan's Remarks for National Crime Victims Week on April 18, 1983* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qLaoayXXwdE>
- Singh, M., & Zahan, M. (2022). *Right to Fair Trial for the Victim – Changing Paradigm in 21st Century*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363484530_Right_to_Fair_Trial_for_the_Victim_-_Changing_Paradigm_in_21st_Century
- Teka, M. (2023). *What Is Blackstone's Formulation in Criminal Law?* | LawInfo. <https://www.lawinfo.com/resources/criminal-defense/what-is-blackstone-s-formulation-in-criminal.html>
- United Nations. (1985). *Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power* [Resolution 40/34]. United Nations Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/107889?ln=en&v=pdf>
- Vinubhai Haribhai Malaviya v. The State of Gujarat, SCC 1346 (Supreme Court of Pakistan 2019).
- Waheed, M. A. (2009). *VICTIMS OF CRIME IN PAKISTAN* (pp. 138-148) [PARTICIPANTS' PAPERS]. THE 144th INTERNATIONAL SENIOR SEMINAR. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.unafei.or.jp/publications/pdf/RS_No81/No81_14PA_Waheed.pdf/
- Wemmers, J.-A. (2012). (PDF) Victims' rights are human rights: The importance of recognizing victims as persons. *ResearchGate*, 71-84. <https://doi.org/10.2298/TEM1202071W>
- Zahan, M., & Singh, M. (2022, March). *Right to Fair Trial for the Victim – Changing Paradigm in 21st Century*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363484530_Right_to_Fair_Trial_for_the_Victim_-_Changing_Paradigm_in_21st_Century
- Zahira Habibullah Sheikh vs State of Gujrat, 3 AIR 1367 (SC 2006).